

Boichuk V.

*Ph.D. in Philology,
Senior Lecturer at the Department of Philology,
The Municipal Higher Educational Institution
“Lutsk Pedagogical College” of the Volyn Regional Council,
Lutsk, Ukraine*

Yefremova N.

*Ph.D. in Philology, Associate Professor,
Associate Professor at the Conversational English Department
Lesya Ukrainka Volyn National University,
Lutsk, Ukraine*

METHODS FOR INVESTIGATING THE PHENOMENON OF PESSIMISM AS A PERSONAL FACTOR OF COMMUNICATIVE INTERACTION

The research into representation of the phenomenon of pessimism in modern English is based on the understanding of language as a unity of three most important modes of its manifestation – language, speech, communication [2].

Pragmatic and contextual analyses may be applied to the investigation of the role of pessimism as a personal factor of communicative interaction. The communicative research program within the anthropocentric paradigm correlates with the communication paradigm as one of the four paradigms of language understanding in the history of philosophical thought (paradigm of name, paradigm of word, paradigm of thought, paradigm of communication, and focuses on language as a means of communication [1, p. 8].

Communicative situation is the starting point of any speech action. It may be defined as a complex set of external conditions of communication and internal states of communicators, which are represented in speech behavior [7, p. 56]. Pessimistic tonality as a basic feature of the mode of communication and as a component of the communicative situation of realization of the speaker's pessimism may be examined with the help of sentiment analysis, which belongs to the class of methods of content analysis. *SentiStrength Software 2.2.* can make it possible to identify the intensity and emotionality of lexical units or text fragment in terms of negative or positive potential. The average value of positive (+ve) / negative (–ve) tonality is the total tonality of the language unit. For example, general tonality of the lexical units *pessimism*, *pessimist*, *pessimistic*, *pessimistically*, which corresponds to the average tonality value, is defined as –1 (tonality+ve (1), tonality –ve (–3)).

The research on the language functioning in communication is impossible without involving the concept of speech act, because speech activity is not only a manifestation of the language system, but also a manifestation of individual experience and individual knowledge of this system [5, p. 36–37]. Speech act is understood as a minimal, relatively independent segment of communication, which is carried out by a specific agent in relation to a specific addressee under specific conditions and with certain intentions [6, p. 109–124]. It is a speech action, which is carried out in accordance with the principles and rules of speech behavior accepted in a particular society. Speech act is always correlated with a speaker as a personality [4, p. 131]. This point of view makes it possible to transfer pessimistic utterances beyond the internal linguistic context and allows to apply the knowledge of communicators about the situation in which communication takes place, their ideas about each other, their communicative experience and background knowledge, i.e. external context, to their analysis.

It is a discourse analysis that may enable a researcher to find out a number of communicative strategies and tactics for expressing pessimism. Communicative strategy is the main factor in the organization of communication, as it reflects the general stereotypes of the process of communicative interaction depending on the conditions of communication and personalities of communicators. As an optimal realization of the speaker's intention to achieve a specific goal of communication, communicative strategy determines the control and choice of certain modes of behavior at a certain stage of communicative interaction, which are aimed at obtaining the desirable or preventing undesirable results (communicative tactics) and their flexible modification in a certain communicative situation [3, p. 118–120].

Thus, pragmatic analysis, which is used to clarify the speech-act specificity of pessimistic utterances, contextual analysis, aimed at defining the functional aspect of linguistic means of representation of the phenomenon of pessimism, content analysis, which helps to find out the pessimistic tonality of the utterance, and discourse analysis, that enables a researcher to highlight strategies and tactics for expressing pessimism, are the basic linguistic methods for investigating pessimism as a personal factor of communicative interaction.

Literature

1. Андрейчук Н. І. Одиниці дискурсу у різних програмах мовознавчих досліджень. *Науковий вісник Дрогобицького державного педагогічного університету імені Івана Франка. Серія : Філологічні науки (мовознавство)*. 2014. № 1. С. 5–10.
2. Бацевич Ф. Нариси з комунікативної лінгвістики. Львів : Львівський нац. ун-т ім. І. Франка, 2003. 280 с.
3. Бацевич Ф. С. Основи комунікативної лінгвістики : підруч. Київ : Вид. центр «Академія», 2004. 344 с.
4. Бацевич Ф. С. Нариси з лінгвістичної прагматики : [монографія]. Львів : ПАІС, 2010. 336 с.
5. Бехта І. А. Дискурс наратора в англійській прозі. Київ : Грамота, 2004. 304 с.
6. Сусов И. П. Лингвистическая прагматика. Винница : Нова Книга, 2009. 272 с.
7. Формановская Н. И. Речевое общение: коммуникативно-прагматический подход. Москва : Русский язык, 2002. 216 с.